

Encountering Violence

The Movement and the Legitimation of Violence at the Eve of Italy's *anni di piombo*

'A student rebellion almost exclusively inspired by moral considerations certainly belongs among the totally unexpected events of this century'

Hannah Arendt¹

'People choose to belong to an identity group, but it is a choice predicated on the strongly held, intensely conceived belief that the individual has absolutely no choice but to belong to that specific group'

Orlando Patterson²

The 1968 global revolutionary upheaval was a generational celebration of spontaneity, a goliardic rebellion to anything perceived as repressive, a breakthrough of the apathy and alienation of post-war Western societies. Generational authority was shattered by the emergence of an antagonistic young culture that felt repressed and oppressed by the cold war conservative society.³ 'Run forward comrade, the old world is behind you', recited one slogan painted on a wall of the Paris commune.⁴ The rebellion was spontaneous because largely unexpected and because, unlike other revolutionary urges, it began neither with a vanguard party nor with workers' uprising.⁵ If anything the movement condemned the 'partytocratic' organization of Western societies. Yet, in Italy the movement ended up creating if not a vanguard party, at least a vanguard *space*, in which several dissident groups decided to embrace clandestine political violence – or what they termed *lotta armata* ('armed struggle') – alongside a certain degree of party-like organization.⁶ Their goal was nothing less than tearing down the bourgeois state. To eradicate the domination of capital on the masses and substitute it with something that was never elaborated in depth, but vaguely recalled the Marxist-Leninist 'dictatorship of the proletariat'. In that 'transitional space' from spontaneous movement to organized violence, personal and local but also transnational encounters with violence mingled to create an explosive amalgam of anger, disillusionment, fear and hope.⁷ Between 1967 and 1969 several domestic and international crucial events for the formation of left-wing violent and clandestine groups took place. The riots at the Berkeley campus, the Colonels' coup in Greece, the overthrowing of Allende, the Vietnam war, the riots at Valle Giulia, the entering of the neo-fascists in the Ferdinando Tambroni government, the Piazza Fontana bombing, the mysterious death of anarchist Giuseppe Pinelli, and the '*autunno caldo*' ('hot autumn') at the FIAT headquarters. This was

all part of that cauldron in which the personal experiences of the people who later chose to become ‘revolutionaries’ mingled, a cauldron that in their view – and to some extent that of the entire movement – seemed to have legitimized violence as a continuation of political agendas.⁸

As a result, between 1969 and the mid-1980s Italy was ensnared in a permanent state of violent social conflict. On the one hand, right-wing extra-parliamentary groups, such as *Ordine Nuovo* (ON) and *Avanguardia Nazionale* (AN), endorsed by obscure individuals allegedly in contact with the secret service apparatus, resorted to terrorism attacking public places with bombs that killed dozens at a time. According to many scholars, although never clarified or incontrovertibly proven by historical evidence, their goal was creating the conditions for a return to a more conservative government coalition and perhaps hampering the continuous growth of the Communist Party (PCI) – a strategy that would soon be known as ‘*strategia della tensione*’ (strategy of tension). On the other hand, left-wing extra-parliamentary and self-defined ‘revolutionary’ groups, such as the *Brigate Rosse*, targeted ‘political enemies’ and kidnapped, kneecapped or killed them cool-headed.⁹ Their goal, so they said, was not terror per se, but revolution. ‘We deluded ourselves’, as a member of the Red Brigades (RB) put it, ‘that the revolution was then possible in Italy’.¹⁰ The figures of this ‘low intensity civil war’ – as some scholar has dubbed it – are cruel.¹¹ These years have become popular in Italy’s collective memory as the *anni di piombo* (‘years of lead’); the lead of the bullets and the bombs that killed some 270 people between 1969 and 1980. According to some estimates, right-wing groups killed 115 people (85 in the Bologna station bombing in August 1980 alone), left-wing terrorists killed 110, whilst the police 29. Add at least 500 people wounded or kneecapped.¹² In 1977, the ISTAT (*Istituto Nazionale di Statistica*) estimated one politically motivated attack every 13 hours for a total of 628 attacks in 1975, but in 1976 that figure nearly doubled to 1198 and increased again dramatically the following year, when a second wave of unrest erupted at Italian universities.¹³ As the *anni di piombo* culminated with the kidnapping of *Democrazia Cristiana* (DC) President and former Prime Minister Aldo Moro in March 1978, the crisis of the Italian political system ran deep. Only a few months before Moro’s tragic death, a Ministry of Interior memorandum alarmingly stated that, ‘The internal security of the state is seriously threatened by subversive extremist right and left wing groups, with the highest level of organization and ideologisation’.¹⁴ American Ambassador in Rome Richard Gardner agreed with this assessment and told Prime Minister Andreotti that terrorism constituted ‘the single most dangerous threat to Italy’s stability’.¹⁵

In a 1984 poll conducted by the Italian newspaper *La Repubblica*, when asked what event of Italy’s twentieth century history would occupy the mind of future historians the most, the majority believed it would be political terrorism.¹⁶ They were right. Unfortunately, given the political and

emotional charge attached to it, Italian scholarship has struggled immensely to overcome partisanship on the subject, while interests on this phenomenon remains scant in the Anglophone one.¹⁷ Recent scholarship has attempted to overcome the partisanship and politicization of previous studies – as well as their search for mono-causal explanations – pointing out how the key to understanding the *anni di piombo* lies in complexity and in overlapping processes of legitimation of violence. A collection of essays by younger Italian historians edited by Simone Neri Serneri has correctly noticed how violence was far from extraneous to the Italian political context of the 1960s, both on the right and the left.¹⁸ Similarly, a ground-breaking study by Gabriele Donato has illustrated how the debate about ‘armed struggle’ was not at all marginal to the discourse of the leftist extra-parliamentary groups that bloomed in those feverish years.¹⁹ Guido Panvini’s *Ordine Nero, Guerriglia Rossa* has also examined the ways in which the extra-parliamentary groups, both on the right and the left, absorbed and projected the rhetoric (and action) of violence.²⁰ Giovanni Ceci, in his extremely dovetailed overview of the existing scholarship, has argued that these studies, coming mostly from a new generation of Italian historians, represent perhaps the first “true historiography” of Italian terrorism.²¹ It is not only younger scholars, however, that one should enlist in this ‘new historiography’; for instance, historian Vladimiro Satta has long contributed to the debate criticizing the tendency of some literature to flirt with conspiracy theories that have sometime captivated even those ‘Truth Commissions’ that were supposed to cast light on the dramatic events of the *anni di piombo*.²²

Against this background, the aim of this study is two-fold. On the one hand, it aims to review a recent (and most welcome) turn in the historiography of Italian terrorism and introduce it to those scholars of terrorism who do not read Italian, with the intent of promoting a much-needed internationalization of the study of Italian terrorism.²³ This study builds on this ‘new’ historiography and focuses on the formative years of those left-wing groups that embraced clandestine political violence. In looking at the choices underpinning the transition from protest to revolutionary armed action, this article aims to disentangle the different layers where those who would then become left-wing ‘revolutionaries’, or ‘terrorists’ according to many Italians – encountered, experienced, and eventually embraced and perpetrated violence for over a decade. This article joins the most recent literature on the topic in arguing that the legitimation of violence within the Italian society happened at different levels and this process of legitimation was crucial in the transition of some members of the movement to clandestine political violence. On the other hand, it aims to place the legitimation of violence taking place in Italy in the late 1960s against the background of the Cold War – something that even these new studies have underestimated. The international context of the Cold

War provided the imagery and the cultural-ideological background against which the mythologisation of violence was resurrected, fomented and transformed in new ways crucial to the personal experience of those men and women who came to believe in the absolute necessity of waging a revolutionary war against the 'state'.

The first section argues for a chronological re-orientation of the study of the emergence of clandestine political violence in Italy that eschews the excessive centrality of the *strage* (massacre) of Piazza Fontana in December 1969 as its starting point – the processes of legitimisation of violence were in place before Piazza Fontana, these were perhaps accelerated but not generated by the bombing.²⁴ The second section analyses how violence was perceived as a dominant feature of the everyday life of Italian students and workers. The final section introduces a different level of analysis: what role in the process of legitimisation of violence did the memory of the *Resistenza* and the mythologisation of violence in the international context of the Cold War play?

Some Reflections on Chronology and Piazza Fontana

Piazza Fontana has often been invested of a paramount importance in the Italian scholarship. One of the most controversial historiographical debates, for instance, has involved the relationship between the 1968 student movement and the formation of clandestine armed groups in the early 1970s.²⁵ The connection between the 1967-69 movement and the armed groups that spread terror and blood all over the country in the 1970s has proved a sensitive topic for Italian historians, particularly those with a radical past. Many leaders of the movement have maintained in their memoirs that the movement was completely extraneous to the season of terrorism that would plague Italy only a few years later.²⁶ In other words, the movement was 'innocent' until Piazza Fontana caused that innocence to be lost. In the aftermath of Piazza Fontana, however, the movement grew convinced that Italy was an oppressive and authoritarian society, to such an extent that many concluded that the Italian state was in fact a terrorist state.²⁷ As one activist of *Lotta Continua* explained, 'The revelation of the *terrorist state* opened up a whole new horizon for our struggle'.²⁸ It is no coincidence that the movement coined the expression '*stragi di stato*' (state massacres) to refer to the bombs that exploded not only in Piazza Fontana, but also on several trains, in train stations and other public places between 1969 and 1980.²⁹ Although the slaughterers were never identified, the movement lay the blame on the state. As Historian Paul Ginsborg put it, 'alerted by investigative journalism and resilient prosecutors, Italian public opinion became ever more convinced that a neo-fascist plot, the so-called "strategy of tension" was afoot'. To the eyes of

the movement it looked like neo-fascists and sections of the secret service were trying to create the conditions to justify further repression, and lead to an authoritarian political turn – perhaps even a military coup.³⁰ ‘State’ became a pejorative and flattened concept onto which all forms of public and private authority were spread: deviant secret services, university rectors, industrialists and politicians. The legitimacy of democracy itself was called into question. The movement did not need any proof.³¹ The perception of a violent terrorist state was so deep-rooted in the leftist intelligentsia that Pier Paolo Pasolini – one of the most prominent Italian intellectuals of the century – denounced it with an open letter to *Corriere della Sera*: ‘I know the names of those responsible for what has been called ‘*golpe*’...I know the names of those responsible for the massacre of Milan of 12 December 1969...I know the names of those who maneuvered both the old fascists that conceived the ‘*golpe*’, and the neo-fascists that executed the early bombings, and finally those ‘unknowns’, who perpetrated the most recent massacres...I know. But I don’t have proofs’.³² This encapsulates one of the keys to accessing the *forma mentis* of the time: the widespread perception of injustice, repression and terror did not necessarily depend upon objective instances, rather on the public interpretation of the events.³³ The movement, and large sectors of public opinion, came to believe that Western societies were no less repressive than on the other side of the Iron Curtain.³⁴ They despised American imperialism and sympathized with the liberation movements in the Third World. Many within the movement felt that that would legitimize a violent reaction on their part.³⁵ Some decided to do so. Adriano Sofri, leader of one these extremist groups (*Lotta Continua*), has given the most vivid and sensible portrait of what Piazza Fontana signified. He maintained that Piazza Fontana meant the ‘loss of innocence’ for a generation. It was that tragedy that irreversibly introduced violence in the daily life of the country. ‘After [Piazza Fontana], we started believing not only in the necessity of violence, but also in its virtue’. ‘Innocents as we were,’ he continued, ‘It was our right to throw the first stone, a right that then became a curse. Then, once you have thrown it, you have lost your innocence. And it is not by chance that you throw another one, and then another one, until that becomes who you are, a stoner’.³⁶

The devious character cast for the state by the movement has also taken its historiographical place under the label of ‘*doppio stato*’ (double state) or ‘parallel state’ (*stato parallelo*) theory.³⁷ According to these scholars, ‘part of the institutional elite’ constituted in a sort of ‘obscure power’ (*potere occulto*) parallel to the formal government intervened to influence Italian politics with the aim of favouring a balance of power that leaned towards the centre-right and therefore kept the Communists out of power.³⁸ According to one of the main exponents of this theory confronted with the rise in popularity of the Communist Party (PCI) and the crisis of the centre-left government the

parallel state first ‘attempted to impose a military regime modelled on the Turkish or Greek examples, then infiltrated right and left wing extremist groups to foment the opposition between extremist forces’ that would make the access of the PCI to government positions impossible and would justify further repression as well as the adjustment of a general political equilibrium on the right-hand side of the political spectrum.³⁹ According to these and many other ‘conspiracy theory’ studies that appeared over the years, the United States, the CIA and NATO lay behind the actions of the ‘parallel state’.⁴⁰

Back in the late 1960s, the PCI had also privately given voice to concerns regarding a possible ‘Greek solution’ for Italy. Even before Piazza Fontana, Luigi Longo, a senior member of the PCI, told the Party that ‘the situation [was] so tense that the military might decide to intervene’.⁴¹ Amateurish plans for such a coup were in fact prepared for July and December 1970 by some officials of the SID, and a retired neo-fascist military Valerio Borghese, leader of the neo-fascist group, *Fronte Nazionale* (FN). Made aware of these plans, the extra-parliamentary left’s perceptions were corroborated. Many came to believe that the CIA, or even the US State Department, was pulling the strings of a complacent puppet – much like Guatemala since 1954, South Vietnam, and the Colonels’ regime in Greece before. These conspiracy theory studies continue to claim this today. Even the President of the ‘*Commissione Stragi*’ (i.e., the Parliamentary Truth Commission investigating the *stragi* taking place between 1969 and 1980) has repeatedly proposed this line of argument.⁴² De Lutiis, amongst others, has argued that, ‘the subversive attempts of the 1960s and 1970s were all accommodated by the American apparatus’, as if the CIA was behind both the left wing revolutionary groups and the right-wing attempts to install an authoritarian regime in Italy, and even behind the killing of Aldo Moro.⁴³

Abundant evidence, however, seems to conclusively dispel any claim of US participation. If anything, the United States was concerned by the prospect of a shift to the right of the Italian political system. The centre-left coalition was seen as the only viable option to maintain law and order, leaving both the communists and the fascists out of government. Ambassador Graham Martin in Rome defined the coup attempts as ‘unrealistic’ and ‘ludicrous’.⁴⁴ A few years later, as rumours of coups mounted anew, CIA Director George Bush, put it even more bluntly: ‘The US has plenty to be concerned about in Italy without the added trouble of a far-right coup attempt or efforts to implicate the US in one. While the attempt would probably fail, it would damage our friends, probably help our adversaries, and have harmful effects in Europe...we ought to take precautions to avoid any idea of US association with such a project’. In the same memorandum, Bush claimed that those on the right in Italy who discussed the possibility of a coup would be simply

delusional in expecting US acquiescence and referred to them as bordering on the ‘mentally unbalanced’.⁴⁵ To be sure, exponents of FN had had contact in 1969 and 1970 with CIA and US Embassy officials. The group was begging the CIA ‘to sit down and at least listen to the group and their proposed solution’. FN wanted an assurance not of support but of American neutrality in case of a coup. The CIA replied that it ‘could not endorse such vague embryonic plans or ideas’. In 1971, a CIA agent reported from Rome that, ‘with its limited resources and comic opera stature of its leader [Borghese], the FN lacks the potential to plan and carry through a coup’.⁴⁶ Thus, the United States and the CIA did not sponsor or support right-wing groups in Italy, as the research of many historians had already shown.⁴⁷ To discard the theory that the CIA or NATO directed a ‘parallel state’ in Italy that exercised a control on terrorist groups does not mean to deny the existence of all forms of connivance between members of the Italian secret services and neo-fascists groups. The degree of such connivance remains uncertain, but it is worth mentioning how even former Minister of Interior Paolo Emilio Tavani told the *Commissione Stragi* that in 1973 he had grown convinced that the neo-fascists had indeed planted the bomb in Piazza Fontana and that the SID (Italian Secret Service) had ‘covered them’.⁴⁸ Proofs of these links remain scant. However, evidence of an ongoing dialogue between the SIFAR (the military secret service) and right-wing extremists from an earlier period invites suspicion. For instance, in an internal SIFAR document entitled ‘Ideas and suggestions for a serious and efficient anti-Communist action in Italy’, one could find embryonic ideas of a ‘strategy of tension’. The document suggested ‘creating groups of youngsters, activists and squads that could use all means,’ including ‘terrorism’ to fight the enemy.⁴⁹ These words give out the sense of hysteria that some within the government apparatus had reached in the aftermath of the 1963 ‘*apertura a sinistra*’ (opening to the left), when the Socialists (PSI) entered government in co-dominium with the DC. After all, it is not necessary to look at secret links between military and extreme right, as it is widely known that in the mid-1960s members of both parties participated in conferences and seminars on revolutionary and counter-revolutionary war, the most famous being the conference at the *Istituto Pollio* in Rome, in which Guido Giannettini – member of the SID later prosecuted in connection to Piazza Fontana – participated.⁵⁰

Yet, continuing to centre the experience of political violence in Italy on Piazza Fontana – like the two interpretative narratives (‘loss of innocence’ and ‘double state’) presented in this section would have it – would be a mistake. For instance, Anna Bravo, former activist and historian, has warned against referring to violence simply in terms of ‘loss of innocence’, as if Piazza Fontana singlehandedly introduced violence in the country and into the movement.⁵¹ Adriano Sofri himself recognized that before Piazza Fontana ‘our mouths were full of violent words’.⁵² Thus, some

elements of continuity between the movement and the extremist organizations existed regardless of Piazza Fontana, which only accelerated a process that was already nesting within the movement.⁵³ In the eyes of the movement violence became not only a choice, but also a necessity, even before Piazza Fontana. Recent studies, like Bravo's as well as Donato's *La Lotta Armata* and Neri Serneri's edited volume *Verso la Lotta Armata*, have pointed out that the key to understanding the *anni di piombo* lies in the disentangling of overlapping processes of legitimation of violence. Once the historiographical impasse caused by the Piazza Fontana-centric narratives offered in the past one realizes that the encounter with violence – perhaps a decisive one – as well as its legitimation preceded the encounter with the idea of state-sponsored terror. The next section examines how to young Italian students, workers, and migrants, violence manifested itself in the quotidian.

Everyday Violence

To the surfacing of young countercultures and the rejuvenation of union struggles in the early-mid 1960s, the Italian government responded uniquely through force and repression, often disproportioned to the dimension of the social phenomena with which it refused to engage.⁵⁴ One of the most important experts on left-wing terrorism, Donatella Della Porta, has focussed much of her scholarship on the interactions between state and social movements and has argued that the radicalization of parts of the movement can be explained – although only in part – through the category of 'protest policing'.⁵⁵ In her studies, Della Porta has found that in the 'early seventies, the state responded to the radicalized left-wing movements with a use of police force that, on several occasions, reverted to the most brutal traditions of the fifties' and that 'the reactive tactics for the control of mass demonstrations encouraged escalation'.⁵⁶ Both quantitative and qualitative analyses of Italy's 'protest policing' support the conclusion that the police repression – even if only due to its perception by the movement – played an important role in the process of radicalization of the movement, and certainly in the legitimation of violence as a substitute for politics and policies. For instance, between 1968 and 1973 the Italian police killed 12 people and injured hundreds during manifestations and rallies, often due to improper and unauthorized use of firearms against unarmed protesters.⁵⁷ As early as 1966, university upheavals had caused the first casualty. Socialist student Paolo Rossi was the unfortunate victim of an increasing polarization within the university between left and right-wing student groups.⁵⁸ The surfacing of a generational – initially apolitical – unease anticipated the larger protests in Italian universities that begun in 1967. Between 1967 and 1968, the students in protest occupied most universities: Rome, Turin, Pisa, Padua and Milan. Their demands

were hardly revolutionary, although their rhetoric often was. They demanded the right to gather in assemblies, to abandon the old-style frontal lectures in favour of seminars in which students and professors could debate more freely, the introduction of more contemporary topics and issues in the courses that were already taught, the right to organize ‘counter-courses’ led by students (as they did during the occupations). In general, the students demanded a more open university that would include the students in the fundamental academic and administrative decisions, and in which professors would treat students as ‘equals and not as servants’, as one student leaflet put it.⁵⁹ Yet, the academic authorities – with some notable exceptions – pandered to intolerant prefects, who urged university rectors to let the police intervene on campus to evacuate the occupied buildings. Minister Taviani went even further and instructed prefects to send in the police on campus even without the rector’s authorization, as provided for by the Italian law. The Italian government treated the protests merely in terms of law and order. To such an extent that one of the PCI leading and more moderate members Giorgio Napolitano expressed his concern about the unprecedented level of ‘police repression in the universities’.⁶⁰ Like in many other Western countries, student occupations and police charges to evacuate buildings with smoke bombs and truncheons became a daily experience. As one of the leaders of the movement put it, ‘The movement neither invented, nor discovered violence. It simply received it’.⁶¹ The epitome of the clash between police and students came with the so-called ‘battle of Valle Giulia’ in Rome. On 29 February 1968, the police expelled the students who had occupied the faculty of Architecture at the University of Rome. On March 1, some 4,000 students armed with rocks and metal bars attacked the building to expel the police that were guarding it. The images of the time leave no doubt about the cruelty of the clashes, which left behind police cars in flames and hundreds of injuries. However, it was not only tragic events like these that perpetuated the view of a repressive state. School deans, university rectors, and conservative press would prove intolerant towards any expression of anti-conformism. A study by historian Guido Crainz has unambiguously shown the unnecessary hatred and reactionary character of response that large sectors of the Italian society poured against the emergence of counter-cultures in Italy.⁶²

To be sure, the student movement developed in Italy with very similar traits to other movements in American, French and German campuses. However, the encounter between students and workers would make the Italian case a peculiarity. It was precisely that peculiarity that bred the most intense and longest-lasting protest movement in post-war Europe. To cement the alliance between students and workers, although differences and diffidence remained strong, was again the encounter with violence and repression. The students ‘discovered’ that ‘authoritarianism finds place

not only in school and university, but in the whole of Italian society, and in particular in the factories; FIAT being the most prominent example'.⁶³ This encounter is masterly depicted in Elio Petri's movie *La classe operaia va in paradiso* ('The working class goes to heaven'). The protagonist, a worker named Lulù Massa, is generally uninterested in politics and a hard worker. However, the encounter outside the factory's gates with radical students who criticized the union for being too mild will turn him into one of the leaders of the protests in his factory. Ennio Furchi, former FIAT worker and symbol of the movement, also recalled, 'The student movement showed the working class that it was now possible to overcome the condition of repression and employment in the factory'. Furchi remembered that when the students distributed leaflets outside the factories, he realized for the first time that 'someone could listen to the problems of the working class and perhaps do something about it'.⁶⁴ The dialogue between workers and students found an informal institutionalization in single factories, for instance in the *Comitati Unitari di Base* (CUB) in the main factories of Milan and Turin, starting with Pirelli. For instance, the history of one of the main leaders of the Red Brigades, Mario Moretti, is intimately connected with the experience of these student-workers 'assemblies'. Moretti was member of one such group at Siemens in Milan. 'We', he recalled, 'were fascinated by the student movement even more than we would like to admit... Soon we would meet the students outside the gates of the factories'. The concept of autonomous democratic and spontaneous assemblies was borrowed from the experience of university occupations. Within a few months, between 1968 and 1969, the unions had largely lost control of the workers' movement. The 'assemblies' directed strikes, protests within the factory, 'self-reduction' of working hours and production. A worker who would join the extremist group *Lotta Continua* recalled, 'The unions negotiate against the exploitation of the working class, but they do not want to abolish it'.⁶⁵ Unionist Bruno Trentin confessed that, 'The unions were completely overwhelmed by the generalization of the struggle which involved workers and students, which was managed by common assemblies outside the gates of the factories'.⁶⁶ Another unionist complained in the summer of 1969: 'I have told the students that they have to be strategic in their battle. They must coordinate with the unions. Because right now they are only dividing the working class! They do not have a direct experience of the factory, in fact they are the children of the *padroni!*'⁶⁷

Exhausting working hours and unbearable working pace to augment productivity, non-existent safety standards, these were the unhealthy and dangerous conditions of Italian factories against which the workers' movement rebelled against. '*Cottimo* (piecework) imposes on the workers the risk to lose their hands under the press,' accused a leaflet distributed by the students at University of Pavia – the fate that awaited Petri's fictional character Lulù Massa.⁶⁸ 'Workers,' Furchi

said, ‘were confronted with violence and repression at all levels.’ This was particularly true for the hundreds of thousands of men and women migrating from South Italy to the industrial centres of the North. Although most of these migrants were hard workers and could not afford to strike, and therefore did not join the struggle, many angry and disillusioned young southerners, who had recently migrated to Milan or Turin, were often the protagonists of the strikes and the ‘assemblies’ that animated the ‘hot autumn’.⁶⁹ Thus, violence was first an ‘intimate’ companion for all workers *within* the factory. The figures of work accidents and injuries speak for themselves. One unionist at the time accused that the phenomenon had reached the ‘dimension of a war’: 12 deaths and 2,463 injuries per day; one accident every 20 seconds, 1 victim every 2 hours of work.⁷⁰ ‘These might sound as the figures of a war bulletin,’ continued the unionist. ‘Behind these cruel figures, there are men and their lives, and yet no one dears to speak about it’.⁷¹ Neurotic episodes, which today we would simply refer to as stress or ‘burnout syndrome’, were the ‘new malaise’ and both doctors and employers struggled to understand the origins of such psychological distress. According to one PCI propagandist short film ‘*La Fabbrica Parla*’, 72% of FIAT workers lamented stress related indispositions.⁷² Giorgio Bocca, one of Italy’s finest journalists at the time, denounced the problem in a now famous article on *Il Giorno*, *La Fabbrica Nevrotica* (‘The Neurotic Factory’). Bocca reported how the stress imposed on Italian workers often degenerated and caused violent retaliatory episodes against those in higher positions in the chain of command, such as engineers or supervisors, who were often insulted and even physically assaulted.⁷³ At the time, Italian factories were heavily guarded, which only enhanced the perception of being prisoners rather than employees. The metaphor of the ‘factory penitentiary’ was anything but uncommon in the memoirs of former workers.

The situation for the workers was not much better outside the factory, in the streets and squares where they reunited to strike and protest. Violent repression of strikes had been a bad habit of the Italian government since the 1950s, but the movement was now much stronger and repression instigated aggressiveness. By 1969-1970, the extra-parliamentary left began to strengthen their *servizi d'ordine* that were to protect the demonstration. The strikes escalation reached a peak in 1969 with an estimated 230 million hours of strikes.⁷⁴ By 1969, the first neo-fascist bombs had exploded on Italian trains and at the Milan fair. Although, the authorities were fully aware of the fact that ‘Demonstrative attacks will be carried out in the next few weeks against public offices...these actions should be conducted by right-wing groups,’ as a document of the Ministry of Interior stated, they still pursued anarchist and left-wing leads.⁷⁵ In a context in which, particularly after Piazza Fontana, many workers and students believed they had discovered ‘the terrorist state’ (*stato terrorista*),

the already proliferating extremist groups at the fringes of the movement took it upon themselves to elaborate a more radical and organized response. In this light, the context of everyday violence that permeated the relationship between the state and its citizens (certainly aggravated by tragic events like Piazza Fontana) constituted the cultural soil in which the radicalization of a minority of the movement took place.⁷⁶

Two further levels of legitimation of violence are analysed in the next section: the memory of the Resistance (i.e., the war of liberation that many Italians '*partigiani*' fought in the north of Italy against the occupying forces and the residue of the fascist state), the liberation wars fought in the Third World against colonial powers (but also the war the North Vietnamese were waging against the American superpower), as well as the 'guerrilla wars' fought by left-wing groups in South America against military regimes, all contributed to creating a nationally and internationally-inspired mythology of violence that heavily influenced the transition of some individuals and groups from the movement to the 'armed struggle'.

Memory, the Cold War and the Mythology of Violence

On 7 July 1960, in Reggio Emilia the police accidentally killed five workers in a demonstration against the new Fernando Tambroni cabinet, which included for the first time the neo-fascist party MSI. That day, a young Prospero Gallinari – future member of the Red Brigades (RB) – was playing in the woods just a few miles away from the city centre where the protest was taking place. In his memoirs, he vividly recalled his father and grandfather's anger and astonishment. They were both loyal communists and former *partigiani* in the most communist city in Italy, and they felt as if a world war and two years of civil war had not been enough to eradicate fascism. The funerals of the five innocent workers turned into another and even wider manifestation. Gallinari, who took part in that manifestation, remembered, 'That anger and that grief ended up being part of my cultural background, alongside the *Resistenza* and its epic symbols. Then would come the liberation movements, Vietnam and so on'.⁷⁷ During that manifestation one of the founders of the RB, Alberto Franceschini, escaped the charge of the police that killed the five men by climbing on a roof. He saw the smoke and heard the shootings distinctively. At that point, he thought that his grandfather was right, 'the Resistance had been betrayed (*tradita*). Only 15 years had passed since the end of fascism and the fascists were back in a government coalition...five communists had been killed. What else could we think?'⁷⁸ In this episode, and particularly in the words of Gallinari and Franceschini, we find two further fundamental tropes that characterized the transition from protest

to clandestine political violence: on the one hand, the memory of the *Resistenza* and the mythology of its betrayal (*Resistenza tradita*); on the other hand, the fascination – one may even say identification – with liberation movements and left-wing guerrilla groups engaged in their battles against oppressive, conservative, and military regimes in the ‘Third World’.

In the 1960s Italy was a highly polarized political system. The PCI was the strongest communist party in Europe and although it enjoyed widespread popular support (over 30%) it was never allowed into government – in the context of the Cold War it would have been unthinkable to have Communists in a NATO government. On the other hand, Italy, unlike Germany, still hosted a weak but growing neo-fascist movement. The way these two groups and their sympathizers *remembered* fascism and World War II were very different. The left turned the resistance into its own pride. It was they the comrades, who freed Italy of the fascists in 1944-45, before the Americans reached the main centres of Northern Italy. The collective memory as constructed and re-embodied in the communist political discourse mythicized both *partigiani* and *resistenza* to the extent that they felt entitled to doubt whether the Italian republic they created could still be considered a democracy. Before Enrico Berlinguer (Secretary of the PCI between 1972 and 1984) proposed renewed collaboration between the PCI and the DC, it was not uncommon to hear PCI members referring to the Italian government in inimical terms. As the Italian political climate heated in 1967 – while the colonels took power in Greece – Giorgio Amendola proudly said, ‘When it came the moment of the armed struggle, of guerrilla, and terrorism, we [communists] did our job...the art we learned back then should not be forgotten’. Referring to the rumours of a possible Greek-style coup in Italy and perhaps anticipating the communist critique of connivance between fascists and the state, he added, ‘We know that we are confronting an enemy, that if it were possible, would recur to other weapons’.⁷⁹ This shows how embracing arms to fight was somewhat of a positive value in the system of beliefs of the Italian left. To be sure, the fascist right was immensely more violent in its daily attempt to ‘hunt the red’, ‘clean up the university’, and organizing bomb attacks. On the extreme right the *Resistenza* was often ignored whether not discarded or even accused of having led Italy to defeat and nearly thrown it into the arms of communism. To dispel any doubts, in late 1969 MSI Secretary Giorgio Almirante auspicated a ‘Greek solution’ for Italy.⁸⁰ Thus, Italy in the 1960s not only did experience a physical battle (fought in the squares, the streets, factories and universities) between ‘black order’ and ‘red guerrilla’, as historian Guido Panvini put it; but it also saw a battle between two competing collective political memories.⁸¹

The memory of the resistance played a crucial role in the personal experiences of some of those who chose the ‘armed struggle’. In chanting slogans against fascism and singing the praise of

armed resistance and revolution these young people were ‘performing’ the past, in the sense that they linked, more or less consciously, their struggle to earlier ones, in particular the *Resistenza*.⁸² In doing so they reinforced and perpetuated the collective memory they had inherited from their communist *partigiani* fathers and grandfathers, friends or teachers, contributing to the creation of a trans-generational and ‘atemporal’ collective identity. Yet both memory and identity were not static or simply received. It was again shaped and re-embodied into new forms, new memories and new identities. The epic battles of the *partigiani* on the Alps were soon substituted by the epic battle of the students in Valle Giulia. Furthermore, one should not forget the emotional role that personal connections with former *partigiani* played. These were at least as important. As Franceschini has confessed in several interviews, it was the *partigiani* who gave him and others their first weapons. ‘They [*partigiani*] were not giving us only their weapons, but also their beliefs, their youth and strength that were no more’.⁸³ In a famous picture taken during the Red Brigades’ first kidnapping, one could distinctively see Franceschini’s hand pointing that gun he had ‘inherited’ at industrialist Idalgo Macchiarini’s face. This performative mechanism is essential to understand, for instance, why a generation who lived through the most prosperous time of Italy’s recent history became convinced of the necessity of a generalized revolution.

It was not only the *Resistenza* to mythicize violence, however. The international context of the Cold War provided plenty of examples that seemed to legitimize the use of violence to achieve political goals. The superpower themselves, arguably, ruled over their respective hemispheres mostly through force in multiple forms. Similarly, the decolonization movement had obtained its successes through civil wars, guerrilla warfare and other forms of political violence. This has been evidenced, for instance, by Simona Colarizi who pointed out how the glorification of the ‘armed struggle’ and ‘violence’ crept in the movement through these national and international myths. Many slogans and signs displayed in the occupied universities around the country in 1968-69 exalted the use of violence: ‘*Il Vietnam vince perché spara*’ (Vietnam wins because it shoots).⁸⁴ Violence was omnipresent in the discourse of the movement, but it also surrounded it. After all, didn’t the entire Cold War international system rely on the threat of mutual annihilation?

In Italy, much like in other countries like France and Germany, the students absorbed the experiences of guerrilla groups around the globe and made them their own. To this regard, French historian Isabelle Sommier has convincingly argued that the international environment fomented a collective ‘belligerent consciousness’, which underpinned the movement’s infatuation with the myth of armed rebellion.⁸⁵ The students grew enamoured with what they perceived as modern days *partigiani*: freedom fighters in former colonies and South America. *Partigiani*, freedom fighters,

workers and students in the occupied universities and factories ‘resisting’ the attacks of the authoritarian state (fascist, terrorist or colonial) ultimately overlapped to become one transnational and trans-temporal anti-systemic identity. In general, the movement appropriated itself of both experiences – resistance and guerrilla – and incorporated them in their consciousness, their ideology and identity. As Luisa Passerini (a leader of the student movement) explained, ‘Our heroes, from the anti-fascist resistance to the revolutionaries in the Third World, embraced and used violence. We started giving for granted that sooner or later it would have been necessary to arm ourselves’.⁸⁶ This is not to suggest that the movement bore a single, homogenous common ideology or cultural baggage. To be sure, the ideological positions within the student movement were variegated. As one student interviewed at the time said, ‘The movement drags and often overcomes us. We moved from a common unease, but there are also differences among us. Some of us would settle for some concessions, others want the revolution’.⁸⁷ Yet, once parts of the movement conglomerated in the extra-parliamentary groups, which would first hegemonise the movement and then give birth to social-revolutionary groups, the cultural paradigm shifted dramatically. Unlike the student movement, what differentiated the myriad of leftist extra-parliamentary groups did not regard *whether* revolution (and thereby violence) was legitimate, but *how* and *when* to achieve it.

In looking for revolutionary tactics and strategies the immediate reference point were not only the liberation movements, but also the Marxist groups that implemented guerrilla tactics against the dictatorships in South America. If one takes the memoirs of the members of the Red Brigades as a case study, these leave no doubt about the role that the Marxist-inspired liberation movements played in their formation and choices. The lexicon, the tactics, the symbols, even the *raison d'être* constantly referred to the international struggle against capitalist imperialism in all its forms. Prospero Gallinari’s book offers probably the best example of this encounter: ‘The sway of Maoist China was rising...it was the red thread connecting the Cuban revolution and the overwhelming anti-colonialist outburst in the Third World that enthused us immensely. There was the Bay of Pigs...the revolutions spreading in Latin America and Africa. The liberation movements in Congo, Algeria, Angola, Guinea-Bissau produced political heroes such as Patrice Lumumba, Agostino Neto or Amilcar Cabral. We understood that it was legitimate to fight and it was possible to win. And above all, after 1964 our interest in the Vietnam War stood out’.⁸⁸

Historian Vladimiro Satta has correctly noticed that the ideological background of the Red Brigades was a peculiar form of internationalist communism that conjugated Marxism-Leninism with the ‘urban guerrilla’ concept inspired by Che Guevara and the Latin American revolutionary movements as well as by Carlos Marighella’s *Minimanual do Guerrilheiro Urbano* (Mini-Manual of

Urban Guerrilla).⁸⁹ As Mario Moretti synthesized: ‘We were in the wake of the communist revolutions. Like Cuba’.⁹⁰ Curcio concurred: ‘We believed that we were moving both in the wakes of the more classic Marxist-Leninist revolutionary tradition and the new perspectives of urban guerrilla practiced by Latin-American groups, or even the Black Panthers in the cities of North America’.⁹¹ Probably the best example of how both the *Resistenza* and the Cold War came to exercise such a powerful fascination on these groups is the symbol of the *Brigate Rosse*. The now famous circled five-pointed star was forged looking both at the national history and at the international struggles of the movements in the Third World. As Franceschini recalled, ‘The star was the symbol of the Brigade Garibaldi [a group of *partigiani*] and the Red Army. It also appeared in the flag of the Vietcong. And above all, it was the symbol of the Tupamaros, the Uruguayan guerrilla movement, our foremost point of reference: a circle with a five-pointed star and the sign “MNT”, *Movimento Nacional Tupamaros*. We simply substituted the sign “MNT” with “Brigate Rosse”’.⁹² In 1967, in one of his first articles *Lotta Continua*’s leader Adriano Sofri gave another testimony of the juxtaposition between students and revolutionaries saying, ‘What happens and will happen in South East Asia concerns us all directly, because their enemy is our enemy, because their slavery covered in blood is our slavery disguised as democracy and progress’.⁹³ The sparkling and fluid context of the movement made it easier for all these ideas to mingle and contribute to a more homogenous lexicon and ideology. For instance, the liberation movements were part of the students’ cultural baggage rather than the workers’. Yet, through the student/workers committees and assemblies, the symbolism of the anti-colonial fights entered the factories. During the manifestation of 1969 in Turin, FIAT workers chanted ‘*Agnelli l’Indocina ce l’hai in officina*’ (‘Agnelli your Indochina is in the factory’). Again, a picture from 1968 captured a graffiti on a factory’s wall in Sesto San Giovanni, an industrial neighbourhood of Milan that eloquently stated: ‘*Il Vietnam è in fabbrica*,’ (‘Vietnam is in the factory’). This image perfectly summarizes the complete identification of the two struggles that the movement operated, one fought in Vietnam by Ho Chi Minh and one in the factories of Italy fought by the groups that elected themselves as vanguard of the movement. One such group was certainly the Red Brigades, which initiated its struggle within the factories of Milan before moving on to more ambitious goals. In their own words, the idea that the *lotta armata* ‘must be led by an organization that is direct expression of the movement’, because of the ‘necessity to undertake new forms of revolutionary struggle’, was central to the rise of the Red Brigades as a vanguard organization of sorts.⁹⁴

Although the focus of this study has been mostly on left-wing revolutionaries, it is worth mentioning here that it was not only the left that took inspiration from what was happening in the

Third World. The war of liberation in Algeria and the terrorist and counterrevolutionary efforts of the French group OAS (*Organisation de l'armée secrète*) were a source of inspiration and admiration for the extremists on the right.⁹⁵ Clemente Graziani, one of the very founders of ON, was enamoured of the OAS and even obtained a membership card, a 'privilege' conceded to few elected. He was persuaded that the left had to be fought on the pitch it had chosen: the revolutionary war. Graziani explained that this would 'obviously imply the possibility of killing elderly people, women and children. These action have been so far considered gross crimes universally repudiated but the logic of a revolutionary war subvert these moral and humanitarian principles'.⁹⁶ Unlike what was happening on the left, where the encounter with the revolutionaries in the Third World was imaginary and ideological, the neo-fascist right theorized a concrete encounter between civilians and the military to indoctrinate and co-opt the military to form a counter-revolutionary monolith very similar to that created in Algeria between the French military and the OAS.⁹⁷ The aforementioned conferences and seminars at the *Istituto Pollio* were one instance of such an encounter.⁹⁸

In sum, the international dimension of Italian terrorism has been a point of discussion since its very inception.⁹⁹ Unfortunately, every time there has been an attempt to inquire those dramatic events from an international point of view, the result has been constantly a frustrating fall into the net of alleged secret services' conspiracies. Those politically on the left would argue that the CIA was designing coup d'état as it did in Latin America. Those on the right would claim that the Soviet Union, the KGB or the Stasi were covertly financing armed struggles all around the world, including terrorists in Western Europe.¹⁰⁰ These arguments have been popularized, for instance, by Claire Sterling's bestseller *The Terror Network* (1981).¹⁰¹

Contrary to such claims, this section has argued that the international and transnational dimension of the phenomenon, if any, did not lay so much in the meddling of the superpowers (or their secret services) as in its ideological dimension. To borrow Benedict Anderson's argument about the formation of national/nationalistic identities, the 'revolutionaries' who exited the movement perceived themselves as a transnational community, an 'imagined community', entirely politically constructed (perhaps subconsciously) to the end of providing legitimation to their actions.¹⁰² As the members of the Red Brigades often maintained when questioned at their trials: if you are fighting a revolution against an oppressive regime, your actions cannot qualify as criminal activities rather as an act of justice, or even heroism. This imagined identity was not foreign to the movement itself – in Italy as much as in France and Germany. However, the terrorists substituted this fascination with a clear political choice to pose themselves in contraposition to the 'state' implementing the same tactics of the revolutionaries, guerrilla groups and liberation armies in Latin

America, Africa and Vietnam, even adopting a similar system of values and, to some extent, means. This is certainly clear not only in Graziani's reference to the 'logic of a revolutionary war', but also in many other horrifying statements by terrorists on the left. 'If necessary,' said Alberto Franceschini about his friend and comrade Prospero Gallinari's obeisance to their cause, 'he would have shot his mother. Probably he would have told her crying: 'I'm sorry mom, but I have to kill you.' And then, he would have done it'.¹⁰³ To be sure, nothing in the Italian context of the early 1970s would have justified similar actions, but in the system of beliefs of the imagined community of global revolutionaries with which they entirely identified, violence had become not only entirely legitimate, but a moral necessity.

Conclusion

This paper has aimed to propose an analytical overview of some themes that are emerging in what one historian has called the 'new historiography' on Italian terrorism.¹⁰⁴ The purpose of such an overview was not only to endorse this welcome 'turn' in methodologies and research inquiries away from the partisanship of an older generation of studies, but also to introduce this historiographical debate to those scholars of terrorism who are not (and cannot be) familiar with the Italian scholarship. This endeavour should stimulate an internationalisation of the various historiographical debates regarding Italian terrorism – its origins, its connections to the movement, the role of the state, the intellectuals and so on.

This study has also cast light on certain salient arguments that have appeared in this 'new historiography'. How did violence become such an ordinary part of the everyday life of Italians between the late 1960s and the mid-1980s? How did individuals and groups decide to embrace clandestine political violence and carry out terrorist attacks? How did they become convinced of the necessity of revolution in Italy in the 1970s? The emerging 'new historiography' has overcome the partisanship and drive for mono-casual explanations and has instead pointed attention on how violence was legitimated at different levels: in the everyday interaction between the movement and the 'protest policing' but also in the competing memories of World War II and the *Resistenza* that divided Italians and generated opposing extremes.

Another level of legitimation appears when focussing on the international and transnational aspects of the history of Italy's political violence – something that is often mentioned but never problematized and analysed. Whenever the Cold War context has been included in the study of Italian terrorism it was magnified to the extent that the whole experience of Italian political violence was reduced to an exogenous imposition of the 'parallel state' other-directed from Washington (or

Moscow). This study has proposed an inclusion of an international and transnational dimension that escapes the theory of ‘double state’ or other conspiracy theories. It argued that the story of Italian terrorism was not only a product of domestic factors – such as the *Resistenza*, the economic difficulties that followed the ‘economic boom’ (*miracolo italiano*), and the mingling of students’ and workers’ struggles brutally repressed by the state in the 1950s and 1960s – but it was also deeply embedded in and part of the international history of the twentieth century. The story of political violence and terrorism in Italy was ultimately a story of overlapping and indiscernible conflicts. The product of a binary dialogue between the local and the global, the national and the international. The Cold War (particularly in its ideological dimension) and the decolonization process in the Third World enhanced and framed the choices of Italian terrorists. On the one hand, the superpowers’ interventionism justified the use of violence as a political tool and legitimized the Manichean view of the world as dominated by imperialist oppressing forces to be countered. On the other hand, the resistance of guerrilla movements in South-East Asia, Africa and Latin America proved that the ‘oppressors’ could be fought and defeated by the ‘oppressed’. The Soviet Union, once ‘Empire of justice’, had, by 1968, lost its lighthouse role for the younger generation of dissidents in Europe.¹⁰⁵ Che Guevara, Mao and Ho Chi Min became the new myths and they had all embraced violence to pursue their ‘just causes’ against imperialism. Reading the memoirs and the documents produced by left-wing groups one can hardly miss that through processes of imitation and inspiration these global instances became part of the local and personal stories.

As new archival material is released and a younger generation of historians advances, the ‘new historiography’ will hopefully continue to move in the direction of complexification, eschewing political partisanship, conspiracy theories, and mono-causal explanations whilst adopting rigorous historiographical methods to cast light on the many unresolved chapters of Italy’s ‘*anni di piombo*’.

Notes

1 Hannah Arendt, *On Violence* (New York: Harcourt, 1969), 43.

2 Orlando Patterson, ‘Implications of Ethnic Identification’, in Charles Fried and Ann Dummett, eds., *Minorities: Community and Identity* (Berlin: Springer-Verlag, 1983), 28–29.

3 Mark Mazower, *Dark Continent: Europe’s Twentieth Century* (London: Allen Lane, 1998), 320–21.

4 On 1968 see, Gerd-Rainer Horn, *The Spirit of ’68: Rebellion in Western Europe and North America, 1956-1976* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2007); Carole Fink et al., eds., *1968: The World Transformed* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 1998); Martin Klimke and Joachim Scharloth, *1968 in Europe: A History of Protest and Activism, 1956-1977* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2008). The slogan is in Angelo Quattrocchi and Tom Nairn, *The Beginning of the End: France,*

May 1968 (New York: Verso, 1968). On the spontaneity and unexpectedness of the movement see Giovanni Arrighi, Terence K. Hopkins, and Immanuel Wallerstein, *Anti-Systemic Movements* (New York: Verso, 2012), esp. 96; and Hannah Arendt, *On Violence*. On the Italian case see for instance, Marcello Flores and Alberto De Bernardi, *Il Sessantotto* (Bologna: Il Mulino, 2003); and, Anna Bravo, *A Colpi di Cuore. Storie del Sessantotto* (Rome: Laterza, 2008).

- 5 Jeremi Suri, *Power and Protest: Global Revolution and the Rise of Detente* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2003), 164.
- 6 Both Mark Mazower and Jeremi Suri raise this notion, see Suri, *Power and Protest*; Mazower, *Dark Continent*. For a definition of ‘clandestine political violence’ one can refer to della Porta’s definition: ‘The extreme violence of groups that organize underground for the explicit purpose of engaging in the more radical forms of collective action’, in della Porta, *Social Movements, Political Violence, and the State*, 4; see also, Donatella della Porta, *Clandestine Political Violence* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2013).
- 7 On this transition see for instance, Donatella Della Porta, *Il Terrorismo Di Sinistra* (Bologna: Il Mulino, 1990); Simone Neri Serneri, ed., *Verso La Lotta Armata. La Politica Della Violenza Nella Sinistra Radicale Degli Anni Settanta* (Bologna: Il Mulino, 2012); Gabriele Donato, «La lotta armata». *Estrema sinistra e violenza: gli anni dell'apprendistato 1969-1972* (Trieste: Irsml Friuli Venezia Giulia, 2012); Guido Panvini, *Ordine Nero, Guerriglia Rossa. La Violenza Politica nell'Italia Degli Anni Sessanta E Settanta* (Turin: Einaudi, 2009); Marica Tolomelli, *Terrorismo e Società. Il Pubblico Dibattito in Italia E in Germania Negli Anni Settanta* (Bologna: Il Mulino, 2007).
- 8 On the uses and misuses of the category of ‘terrorism’ as opposed to ‘political violence’ and ‘clandestine political violence’ see, Donatella della Porta, *Social Movements, Political Violence, and the State: A Comparative Analysis of Italy and Germany* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2006); and, Donatella Della Porta, *Clandestine Political Violence* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2013).
- 9 On the dichotomy between ‘black’ and ‘red’ terrorism see the groundbreaking study by Panvini, *Ordine Nero, Guerriglia Rossa*.
- 10 Franceschini, *Che Cosa Sono Le BR*, 30. Other terrorists made similar statements, see for instance, brigadist Nitta said: ‘My political culture was dominated by a sensation of the inevitability of revolution,’ in Diego Novelli and Nicola Tranfaglia, *Vite Sospese. Le Generazioni del Terrorismo* (Milan: Rizzoli, 2007), 191.
- 11 On the heated debate about whether the *anni di piombo* deserved to be labeled as ‘civil war’ see, Giovanni Fasanella and Giovanni Pellegrino, *La Guerra Civile* (Milan: Rizzoli, 2005); Virgilio Ilari, *Guerra Civile* (Rome: Ideazione, 2001); Fulvio Bellini and Gianfranco Bellini, *Il Segreto Della Repubblica* (Milan: Selene, 2005); Marc Lazar and Marie-Anne Matard-Bonucci, *L'Italie Des Années de Plomb* (Paris: Editions Autrement, 2010); Alessandro Orsini, *Anatomy of the Red Brigades: The Religious Mind-set of Modern Terrorists*, trans. Sarah J. Nodes (Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 2011).
- 12 These are the numbers reported in Orsini, *Anatomy of the Red Brigades*, 1. For a comparison see also, Mauro Galleni, *Rapporto Sul Terrorismo. Interventi di Giulio Andreotti, Franco Ferrarotti, Nicola Tranfaglia*. (Milan: Rizzoli, 1981); Luigi Manconi, *Terroristi Italiani. Le Brigate Rosse e La Guerra Totale 1970-2008* (Milan: Rizzoli, 2008), 22; Donatella Della Porta and Maurizio Rossi, *Cifre crudeli: bilancio dei terrorismi italiani* (Bologna: Istituto di studi e ricerche Carlo Cattaneo, 1984). Della Porta counts 179 victims of left-wing terrorism up to 1983, Donatella della Porta, *Social Movements*, 128. The phrase ‘anni di piombo’ was not coined in Italy, but in Germany. It is a translation from the German ‘Bleierne Zeit’, which is the title of a film by Margarethe von Trotta, *Die Bleierne Zeit*, (Berlin: Eberhard Junkersdorf, 1981). Many historians, particularly those who participated in the movement, reject the notion that this period of political ferment should be reduced to the label of ‘anni di piombo’ as this emphasizes only the most violent aspects of a broader experience, see for instance, Bravo, *A Colpi di Cuore*; and, Giovanni De Luna, *Le Ragioni di un Decennio, 1969-1979* (Milan: Feltrinelli, 2010)
- 13 Ministero degli Interni, Direzione Pubblica Sicurezza, ‘Andamento della criminalità: situazione aggiornata al II bimestre 1977,’ undated (ca. Mar. ’77), Ministero dell’Interno (MI), Gabinetto (GAB) 1976-1980, box 66, Archivio Centrale dello Stato (ACS), Rome.
- 14 Appunto Ministero degli Interni, ‘Appunto sullo stato dell’ordine e della sicurezza pubblica e sulle misure da adottare,’ undated (ca. ’77), Presidente del Consiglio dei Ministri (IV-V Governo), busta 119, ‘Ordine Pubblico 1976-77’, Fondo Aldo Moro (FAM), ACS.
- 15 Consigliere Diplomatico, Presidenza del Consiglio dei Ministri, Appunto per il Presidente, 22 Mar. 1978, ‘Incontro con Gardner’, Prat. 323 ‘Stati Uniti d’America’, S. II ‘Personalità 1952-2007’, b. 598, f. ‘Richard Gardner’, Fondo Giulio Andreotti (FGA), Archivio Istituto Luigi Sturzo (AII.S), Rome.
- 16 The poll is quoted in Leonard Weinberg and William Lee Eubank, *The Rise and Fall of Italian Terrorism* (Boulder, CO: Westview Press, 1989), 5. Although operating a clear distinction between competing concepts such as ‘political violence’, ‘terrorism’ and ‘guerrilla warfare’ is not essential to this study, three working definitions can be provided here. Bruce

Hoffman argues that: ‘Terrorism is ineluctably political in aims and motives, violent – or, equally important, threatens violence, designed to have far-reaching psychological repercussions beyond the immediate victim or target, conducted by an organization with an identifiable chain of command...’, see Bruce Hoffman, *Inside Terrorism*, 2nd ed., (New York: Columbia University Press, 2006), 43. Donatella della Porta has defined political violence as the ‘repertoires of collective action that involve great physical force and cause damage to an adversary in order to impose political aims,’ these actions, operationally, can include: ‘Rioting, when unorganized disorder leads to damage to property; violent confrontation, when members of opposing political groups fight with one another; clashes with the police, when protestors interact violently with the police; violent attacks directed against persons, when one political group attacks another group, or members of the elite or the public, causing injuries or deaths; random violent attacks, when organized violence is directed against persons, regardless of their political or social identities; armed seizure of places or people, including armed trespassing, holdups, and hijacking.’ See della Porta, *Social Movements, Political Violence, and the State*, 2-4; and, Donatella della Porta and Sidney Tarrow, ‘Unwanted Children. Political Violence and the Cycle of Protest in Italy. 1966-1973’, *European Journal of Political Research* 14 (1986): 607-32. Richard English has defined ‘guerrilla violence’ as ‘an irregular war carried on by small bodies of men acting independently’. See Richard English, *Terrorism: How to Respond*, (New York: Oxford University Press, 2009), 12-13.

- 17 There are of course exceptions, although most studies were published as far back as in the latter half of the 1980s. See for instance, Richard Drake, *The Revolutionary Mystique and Terrorism in Contemporary Italy*, (Bloomington, IN: Indiana University Press, 1989); Richard Drake, *The Aldo Moro Murder Case* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1995); Alison Jamieson and Richard Clutterbuck, *The Heart Attacked: Terrorism and Conflict in the Italian State* (New York: Marion Boyars Publ., 1989); David Moss, *The Politics of Left-Wing Violence in Italy, 1969-85*, 1989 (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 1989); Leonard B. Weinberg and William L. Eubank, *The Rise and Fall of Italian Terrorism* (Boulder, CO: Westview Press, 1987); Robert C. Meade, *Red Brigades: Story of Italian Terrorism* (Basingstoke, Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan, 1989). More recent studies have dealt with right-wing terrorism in Italy, for instance, Anna Cento Bull, *Italian Neofascism: The Strategy of Tension and the Politics of Nonreconciliation*, (London: Berghahn Books, 2011).
- 18 Simone Neri Serneri, ‘Contesti e strategie della violenza e della militarizzazione nella sinistra radicale,’ in Serneri ed., *Verso La Lotta Armata*, 11–63.
- 19 Donato, *La lotta armata*.
- 20 Panvini, *Ordine Nero, Guerriglia Rossa*.
- 21 Ceci, *Il Terrorismo Italiano*.
- 22 His most recent contribution is, Vladimiro Satta, *I Nemici della Repubblica: Storia degli Anni di Piombo*, (Milan: Rizzoli, 2016).
- 23 On the necessity to internationalize the research on terrorism see, Robert Gerwarth and Heinz-Gerhard Haupt, ‘Internationalising Historical Research on Terrorist Movements in Twentieth-century Europe,’ *European Review of History: Revue Européenne D’histoire* 14, no. 3 (2007): 275–281; Cornelissen, *Il Decennio Rosso*, 19–25; Giovanni Mario Ceci, *Il Terrorismo Italiano: Storia di un Dibattito* (Rome: Carrocci, 2017), 330.
- 24 On 12 December 1969, a bomb exploded in the *Banca Nazionale dell’Agricoltura* located in Piazza Fontana in Milan, killing 17 and wounding 88. That same night, anarchists Giuseppe Pinelli and Pietro Valpreda were arrested. The police had ‘proofs’ that seemed to confirm that the anarchists were responsible for the bombing. On December 15, Pinelli mysteriously died falling from the window of police commissioner Luigi Calabresi’s office. Soon, however, it became apparent that the anarchists had nothing to do with the bombing. Neo-fascist groups, particularly ON, covered by members of the Italian secret service (SID) were more likely to be at blame. For a detailed narrative of Piazza Fontana see, Giorgio Boatti, *Piazza Fontana: 12 dicembre 1969: il giorno dell’innocenza perduta* (Milan: Feltrinelli, 1993).
- 25 For an overview of the debate see, Ceci, *Il Terrorismo Italiano*, 180-199.
- 26 See, Adriano Sofri, ‘Tutto parti da Piazza Fontana. Poi lanciammo la prima pietra’, *Corriere della Sera*, 2 Apr. 2004. For an opposing view see, Bravo, *A Colpi di Cuore*. See also, Marco Revelli, ‘Movimenti Sociali e Spazio Politico’, *Storia dell’Italia Repubblicana*, Vol. II, 2, (Turin: Einaudi, 1995), 383-476.
- 27 This can be seen in numerous contemporary writings of left-wing extra-parliamentary groups; see for instance, Edoardo di Giovanni, Marco Ligini, Edoardo Pellegrini, *La Strage di Stato*, (Milan: Odradek, 2006); this was a pamphlet originally published in 1970 unanimously. Its content is discussed at length in Giannulli, *Bombe a Inchiostro*, 40-61; for a different interpretation see, Satta, *I Nemici della Repubblica*, ch.3.

- 28 Marco Ravelli quoted in, Aldo Cazzullo, *I Ragazzi che Volevano Fare La Rivoluzione. 1968-1978. Storia Critica di Lotta Continua* (Milan: Sperling & Kupfer, 2006), 91. Giorgio Boatti, *Piazza Fontana: 12 dicembre 1969: il giorno dell'innocenza perduta* (Milan: Feltrinelli, 1993).
- 29 On the importance of this semantic expression see Marco Grisogni, 'La Strage è di stato. Gli anni Settanta, la violenza politica e il caso italiano,' in Serneri (ed.), *Verso la lotta armata*, 93–116.
- 30 Paul Ginsborg, *A History of Contemporary Italy: Society and Politics, 1943-1988* (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2003), 334.
- 31 In Italy, the debate whether a 'strategy of tension' ever existed and whether individuals connected to the Italian secret services were ever involved in the 'stragi' remains highly divisive and inflammatory. Giovanni Pellegrino, Chairman of the Parliamentary Commission that investigated the 'stragi', has repeatedly argued that the 'strategy of tension' existed and it was even formalized in a series of conspiratory meetings involving right-wing extremists and members of the army and secret services. See, Giovanni Pellegrino, *Segreto Di Stato. La Verità Da Gladio Al Caso Moro* (Turin: Einaudi, 2000). Very recently, Prime Minister Matteo Renzi issued an executive order demanding the declassification of all documents related to the 'stragi', but to this day the evidence corroborating the thesis of the movement remain thin at best. However, the Corte di Cassazione (Supreme Court) has ruled with court's judgment n. 21998/2005 that members of the neo-fascist group Ordine Nuovo (ON) "bear the responsibility for the bombing at Piazza Fontana, although they have been acquitted in previous trials." It also reached the conclusion that the bombing was indeed part of a "well-consolidated subversive program" implemented by right-wing extra-parliamentary groups like ON. Although Guido Ginannettini, member of the secret services, was originally found guilty in 1979 by the court of Catanzaro and then acquitted in 1981, the suspicions on the involvement of the secret services have not withered. For a more critical view see, Vladimiro Satta, *I Nemici della Repubblica*,
- 32 Pier Paolo Pasolini, 'Cos'è questo golpe? Io so.' *Corriere della Sera*, 14 Nov. 1974.
- 33 I'm referring here to Tolomelli, *Terrorismo e Società*, 16–18. See also, Bert Klandermans, Hanspeter Kriesi, and Sidney G. Tarrow, *From Structure to Action: Comparing Social Movement Research Across Cultures* (London: JAI Press, 1988).
- 34 On the sympathetic attitudes of Italian society towards the more extremist ideas of the left-wing extra-parliamentary groups see, Drake, *The Revolutionary Mystique*.
- 35 This emerges clearly from an overview of the writings of groups like Lotta Continua and Potere Operaio, amongst others, at the time. The best analysis of these writings is Donato, *La lotta armata*. Della Porta also points out how both Italian and German 'revolutionaries' identified their battle with that of the guerrilla groups of the Third World; see della Porta, *Social Movements, Political Violence, and the State*, 132.
- 36 Sofri, 'Tutto partì da Piazza Fontana'.
- 37 Although the term 'doppio stato' was coined by Renzo De Felice, but he did not refer to obscure powers controlling Italian politics, but simply to the importance the Atlantic choice that Italy made in 1949 continued to influence its history until the end of the Cold War; see, Franco De Felice, 'Doppia Lealtà e Doppio Stato' *Studi Storici* 30:3 (July-September 1989): 493-563. Other scholars, however, have instead turned the term on its head to refer to a 'parallel state' that worked beyond the constitutional law to ensure that Italy would continue to exclude the PCI from power by infiltrating and exploiting the terrorist groups both on the left and the right; see for instance, Nicola Tranfaglia, 'Un Capitolo del "Doppio Stato". La Stagione delle Stragi e dei Terrorismi (1969-1984), in *Storia dell'Italia Repubblicana*, Vol. III, 2, (Turin: Einaudi, 1995), 7-80; Tranfaglia, 'Sulle Cause e Sui Misteri del Terrorismo in Italia', *Studi Storici*, Vol.30:2 (1989): 565-578. For a critique of these theories see, Giovanni Sabbatucci, 'Il Golpe in Agguato e il Doppio Stato', in G. Belardelli, L. Cafagna, E. Galli della Loggia and G. Sabbatucci, *Miti e Storie dell'Italia Unita*, (Bologna: Il Mulino, 1999), 211.
- 38 Paolo Cucchiarelli and Aldo Giannulli, *Lo Stato Parallelo. L'Italia "Oscura" nei Documenti e nelle Relazioni della Commissione Stragi*, (Rome: Gamberetti, 1997), 18.
- 39 Tranfaglia, 'Un Capitolo del "Doppio Stato"', 10.
- 40 Even beyond the literature on the 'doppio stato' (see note above), the conspiracy literature is massive. See for instance, Sergio Flamigni, *La Tela Del Ragno. Il Delitto Moro* (Milan: Kaos, 2003); Sergio Flamigni, *Trame Atlantiche. Storia Della Loggia Massonica Segreta P2* (Milan: Kaos, 2005); Giuseppe De Lutiis, *Il Golpe Di Via Fani. Protezioni Occulte e Connivenze Internazionali Dietro Il Delitto Moro* (Milan: Sperling & Kupfer, 2007); Sandro Provvissionato, *Misteri d'Italia* (Bari: Laterza, 1993); Giovanni Fasanella and Rosario Priore, *Intrigo Internazionale. Perché La Guerra in Italia. Le Verità Che Non Si Sono Mai Potute Dire* (Verona: Chiarelettere, 2010).

- 41 Verbale della Direzione PCI del 2 luglio 1969, intervento di Luigi Longo, MF (microfiche) n. 6, p. 1778, Organismi di Direzione: Direzione PCI, Archivio Partito Comunista Italiano (APCI), Archivio Fondazione Istituto Gramsci (AFIG).
- 42 Pellegrino, *Segreto Di Stato*.
- 43 Ibid., and, De Lutiis, *Il Golpe di Via Fani*, 92.
- 44 Telegram 1715 US Embassy in Rome (Ambassador Martin) to US State Department, 'Alleged Attempt at Coup d'État,' 19 Mar. 1971, RG 59, Central Files Foreign Policy, POL 21, b. 2395, National Archives and Records Administration (NARA), Washington, DC
- 45 See, Ibid; and, CIA, Memorandum Director of Central Intelligence George Bush to Brent Scowcroft (State), 'Far Right Coup Plotting in Italy,' 29 Apr. 1976, CIA Records Search Tool (CREST), NARA.
- 46 CIA post Rome to CIA Chief EUR, 'Alleged Role in Coup Plans of Valerio Junio Borghese,' 6 Aug. 1970, CIA-FOIA; and CIA post Rome, Intelligence Information Cable, 'The National Front: An Ineffectual Right-Wing Organization Often Accused of Planning a Coup,' 19 Feb. 1971, CIA-FOIA.
- 47 Vladimiro Satta, 'I Collegamenti Internazionali del Terrorismo Rosso Italiano,' *Nuova Storia Contemporanea* 11, no. 6 (2007): 23–52; Tobias Hof, *Staat und Terrorismus in Italien 1969-1982* (Munich: Oldenbourg Wissenschaftsverlag, 2011).
- 48 Deposition by former Ministry of Interior Paolo Emilio Tavani in Senato della Repubblica e Camera dei Deputati, Commissione parlamentare d'inchiesta sul terrorismo in Italia e sulle cause della mancata individualizzazione dei responsabili delle stragi, XIII Legislatura, Doc. XXIII n. 64, Vol. II Tomo II, Resoconto stenografico della 24esima seduta del 1 luglio 1997, pp. 381-99. Furthermore, documentation gathered during the numerous trials undertaken between 1972 and 2005 seems to prove quite convincingly the existence of connivance between members of the Italian secret service and neo-fascists groups. The degree of such connivance remains uncertain, but it is worth mentioning how prosecutor Gerardo D'Ambrosio, who led the first judicial investigation on the events of 1969, had no doubts when asked about the role of SID (Italian Secret Service) in the so-called 'strategy of tension' he replied: 'Certainly it tolerated and favoured right-wing terrorists, perhaps it was even a partner in crime', quoted in Paolo Biondani, 'La verità su Piazza Fontana? La chiederei a Rauti e Andreotti,' *Corriere della Sera*, 28 Apr. 2005.
- 49 Renzo Rocca (Ufficio REI, Sifar) to Giovanni Allavena (Ufficio D, Sifar), 'Idee e suggerimenti per una serie, efficiente e globale attività anti-comunista in Italia,' 12 Sep.1963. This document was acquired by the Court of Brescia in connection to the trial related to the strage of Piazzale della Loggia (1974) and attached to Giacomo Pacini, 'Settembre 1963: così i servizi segreti pianificavano la strategia della tensione,' Istituto Storico Grossetano della Resistenza e dell'Età Contemporanea (ISGREC).
- 50 Anna Cento Bull, *Italian Neofascism: The Strategy of Tension and the Politics of Nonreconciliation* (London: Berghahn Books, 2011), 113-4. For a brief summary of these events see, Vladimiro Satta, *I Nemici della Repubblica: Storia degli Anni di Piombo in Italia* (Milan: Rizzoli, 2016), esp. ch. 1.
- 51 Bravo, *A Colpi Di Cuore*.
- 52 Sofri, 'Tutto partì da Piazza Fontana.'
- 53 Besides Bravo's book one should refer to, Marco Grispigni, *Elogio dell'Estremismo: Storiografia e Movimenti* (Rome: Manifestolibri, 2000); and, Simona Colarizi, *Storia dei Partiti nell'Italia Repubblicana* (Rome: Laterza, 1999).
- 54 Guido Crainz, *Il Paese Mancato. Dal Miracolo Economico Agli Anni Ottanta* (Rome: Donzelli, 2003).
- 55 Della Porta, *Social Movements, Political Violence, and the State*, 60-74.
- 56 Ibid., 60.
- 57 Serneri, *Verso La Lotta Armata*; Della Porta and Rossi, *Cifre crudeli*; Ginsborg, *Contemporary Italy*, 256–58. Evidently violent repression preceded the outburst of the cycle of student protests in the second half of the 1960s. For instance, in the summer of 1960, the formation of a new government led by Ferdinando Tambroni with Parliamentary support by the neo-Fascist MSI threw Italy in a state of near civil war with raging protests spreading all over the country. After a massive anti-fascist manifestation in Genoa on 30 June in which police and protesters came to clash quite violently, the police opened fire on unarmed civilians in Reggio Emilia, in Licata (Sicily), in Rome, Palermo and Catania killing 9 people and injuring many others. See, Mazower, *Dark Continent*, 317; Philip Cooke, *Luglio 1960. Tambroni e la repressione fallita* (Milan: Teti, 2000).
- 58 Panvini, *Ordine Nero, Guerriglia Rossa*.

- 59 Flyer of the students of Turin University, 21 Nov. 1968, MI GAB 1967-70, b.347, f. 15883/81, ACS.
- 60 Giorgio Napolitano in Verbale della Direzione del PCI del 24 Marzo 1969, 24 Mar. 1969, MF6, p.1290, APCI, AIG.
- 61 Guido Viale, *Il Sessantotto fra rivoluzione e restaurazione* (Milan: Mazzotta, 1978), 79.
- 62 Crainz, *Il Paese Mancato*. For an introduction to the Italian counter-cultures of the 1960s see Alessandro Cavalli and Carmen Leccardi, 'Le culture giovanili,' in Francesco Barbagallo et al. (eds.), *Storia dell'Italia Repubblicana*, vol. III, (Turin: Einaudi, 1997), 709-800. On the 'capelloni' see Diego Giacchetti, 'Ribellismo giovanile e manifestazioni di violenza nell'Italia degli anni Sessanta,' in Cornelissen et al., *Il Decennio Rosso*, 51-70. The hatred reactionism described by Crainz shine through an overview of the Italian press at the time. For instance, like anywhere else in the Western hemisphere, in the mid-1960s young Italians had begun to grow long hair and listen to rock music. The conservative press immediately launched a campaign against what they begun to call 'capelloni', suggesting that the police should lock them away or at least 'disinfect and shave them'. The quote is from an article that appeared on the *Corriere della Sera* on 6 November 1965 as quoted in Crainz, *Il Paese Mancato*, 193. The conservative press wished for them to fall from the long staircase of *Trinità dei Monti* where they used to gather and 'break their neck'. *Corriere della Sera* rejoiced at the news of the police commissioner deciding to intervene more vehemently to 'clean up' the city and even auspicated a tighter control of the borders because, 'no one with long hair should enter in Italy (sic)'. See, Paolo Bugalli, 'I capelloni e l'ordine pubblico,' *Corriere della Sera*, 5 Nov. 1965.
- 63 Flyer of the Student Movement of Turin, 'Perché gli student intervengono nella lotta operaia', 5 Apr. 1968, in MI GAB 1967-70, b. 163, f. 13347/81, ACS.
- 64 Documentary by Alberto Lauriello and Lino De Serriis, 'La Fabbrica' (The Factory), Rome: Circoli del cinema Arci, Centro Sperimentale di Cinematografia, 1970, in Archivio Audiovisivo Movimento Operaio e Democratico/Audiovisual Archive of the Democratic and Labour Movement (AAMOD), online.
- 65 Crainz, *Il Paese Mancato*, 350.
- 66 Ibid., 330.
- 67 Lauriello, De Serriis, Documentary, 'La Fabbrica'.
- 68 Crainz, *Il Paese Mancato*, 270.
- 69 Lauriello, De Serriis, 'La Fabbrica'.
- 70 Paola Scarnati, Claudio Olivieri, Documentary, '1969 Autunno Caldo', (Rome: AAMOD, 2009), AAMOD.
- 71 Ibid.
- 72 Antonio Bertini, short film, 'La Fabbrica Parla', (Rome: Sezione stampa e propaganda direzione Pci, Unitelefilm, 1968), AAMOD.
- 73 Giorgio Bocca, 'La Fabbrica Nevrotica', *Il Giorno*, 27 Feb. 1968.
- 74 Crainz, *Il Paese Mancato*, 325. For instance, in Battipaglia in 1969, people protested the closure of most preserve factories, which left hundreds of thousands jobless. The police opened fire on the protesters and killed two men, while smoke bombs, truncheons and charges with military vehicles injured hundreds. At the tragic news of the victims the entire population of Battipaglia invaded the streets, attacked the police station and burned down the town hall. Within a few hours, the unions and the student assemblies flooded the streets of the main urban centres demanding the government to unarm the police. In Parliament, even members of the government endorsed the motion proposed by the PCI. Just a few months back, two farm hands were killed in Avola during a blockade of the main roads surrounding the city. Again, the police station was put under siege from the population. On new years' eve students of *Potere Operaio* organized a 'solidarity manifestation' in remembrance of the two workers killed in Avola. The police again shot on the protesters nearly killing a 17-year-old boy. In November at the peak of the 'hot autumn' policemen Antonio Annarumma was killed in Milan during a manifestation. The police threatened to march on the university to avenge Annarumma's death. Neo-fascist groups did so. See, Ibid.
- 75 Appunto del Ministero degli Interni, 29 January 1969, in MI GAB 1967-1970, b.354, f.15584/69, ACS.
- 76 This is also the conclusion reached by some scholars including, for instance,
- 77 Prospero Gallinari, *Un Contadino Nella Metropoli. Ricordi di un Militante Delle Brigate Rosse* (Milan: Bompiani, 2008), 28-30.
- 78 Franceschini, *Che Cosa Sono Le BR*, 22-23.

- 79 Giorgio Amendola, 'Cambiare la condizione operaia nella fabbrica, nella società, nello Stato,' Turin, 9-10 Dec. 1967, quoted in Marco Scavino, 'La Piazza e la forza. I percorsi verso la lotta armata dal Sessantotto alla metà degli anni Settanta,' in Serneri, *Verso La Lotta Armata*, 117–118.
- 80 Crainz, *Il Paese Mancato*, 362.
- 81 Panvini, *Ordine Nero, Guerriglia Rossa*.
- 82 On performative memory see, Karin Tilmans, Frank van Vree, and Jay Winter, eds., *Performing the Past: Memory, History, and Identity in Modern Europe* (Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press, 2010).
- 83 Alberto Franceschini, *Mara, Renato E Io* (Milan: Mondadori, 1994), 30.
- 84 Simona Colarizi, *Storia del Novecento Italiano. Cent'anni di entusiasmo, di paure, di speranza*, (Milan: Rizzoli, 2000), 408-9.
- 85 Isabelle Sommier, 'La Legittimazione della Violenza. Ideologie e Tattiche della Sinistra Extra-Parlamentare,' in Serneri, *Verso La Lotta Armata*, 265-285; see also, Isabelle Sommier, *La violence politique et son deuil* (Rennes: Presse Universitaire de Rennes, 2008).
- 86 Luisa Passerini, *Autoritratto di Gruppo* (Milan: Giunti, 1998), 157
- 87 This excerpt is from a series of interviews with students conducted by Giorgio Bocca in March 1968 quoted in Crainz, *Il Paese Mancato*, 235.
- 88 Gallinari, *Contadino Nella Metropoli*, 37–8.
- 89 See, Carlos Marighella, *Mini-Manual of the Urban Guerrilla*, (first published as a pamphlet in June 1969); Che Guevara, *Guerrilla Warfare*, (New York: Monthly Review Press, 1961). For an historical analysis and overview on the role of these publications see, Alberto Martin Alvarez and Eduardo Tristán, eds., *Revolutionary Violence and the New Left: Transnational Perspectives* (London: Routledge, 2017), esp. ch. 3-4.
- 90 Mario Moretti, *Brigate Rosse. Una Storia Italiana* (Milan: Mondadori, 2007), 36.
- 91 Renato Curcio, *A Viso Aperto* (Milan: Mondadori, 1995), 7.
- 92 Franceschini, *Che Cosa Sono Le BR*, 78–9.
- 93 Adriano Sofri, 'Il Vietnam e Noi,' *Il Potere Operaio*, Vol. I n. 2, 7 Jun. 1967.
- 94 Comunicato BR n.1, ca. Mar. 1971, attached to Appunto del Ministero degli Interni, 'Le Brigate Rosse,' 16 Dec. 1976, in b. 119, FAM, ACS.
- 95 Gianni S. Rossi, 'L'influenza della guerra d'Algeria sull'estrema destra italiana,' in Angelo Ventrone, ed., *I dannati della rivoluzione: Violenza politica e storia d'Italia negli anni Sessanta e Settanta* (Macerata: EUM, 2010), 21-39.
- 96 Graziani as quoted in Franco Ferraresi, 'Il rosso e il nero: terrorismi a confronto' in Alessandro Campi and Ambrogio Santambrogio, eds., *Destra e Sinistra: Storia e fenomenologia di una dicotomia politica* (Rome: Antonio Pellicani Editore, 1997), 197-8. On Graziani's life see Sandro Forte, ed., *Clemente Graziani: la vita, le idee* (Rome: Settimo Sigillo, 1972).
- 97 Rossi, 'L'influenza della guerra d'Algeria sull'estrema destra italiana'; and, Satta, *I nemici della Repubblica*.
- 98 A balanced view of the role of these meetings in what would happen in Italy during the *anni di piombo* is Satta, *I nemici della Repubblica*.
- 99 A few examples from the Italian scholarship are, Priore, *Intrigo Internazionale*; Giovanni De Lutiis, *Storia dei Servizi Segreti in Italia* (Rome: Editori Riuniti, 1991); and, Flamigni, *Trame Atlantiche*. Rocco Turi, *Gladio Rossa. Una Catena Di Complotti e Delitti, Dal Dopoguerra Al Caso Moro* (Venice: Marsilio, 2004); Antonio Selvatici, *Chi Spiava i Terroristi. KGB, STASI-BR, RAF. I Documenti Negli Archivi Dei Servizi Segreti dell'Europa Comunista* (Milan: Pendragon, 2010).
- 100 Turi, *Gladio Rossa*; Selvatici, *Chi Spiava i Terroristi*. See also Christopher Andrew and Vasili Mitrokhin, *The Sword and the Shield: The Mitrokhin Archive and the Secret History of the KGB* (New York: Basic Books, 1999).
- 101 Claire Sterling, *The Terror Network: The Secret War of International Terrorism* (New York: Henry Holt & Co., 1981).
- 102 Benedict Anderson, *Imagined Communities* (New York: Verso, 1983).
- 103 Franceschini, *Che Cosa Sono Le BR*, 37.
- 104 Ceci, *Il Terrorismo Italiano*, 330.

105 I'm referring here to the distinction between empire of liberty and empire of justice by Odd Arne Westad, *The Global Cold War: Third World Interventions and the Making of Our Times*, (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2007). On the declining symbolic role of the USSR see Silvio Pons, *La Rivoluzione Globale. Storia Del Comunismo Internazionale 1917-1991* (Turin: Einaudi, 2012), 325-98.